

Comparative Study and Qualitative Phytochemical Screening of Different Extracts of *Psidium guajava* Leaf

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a comparative analysis of several extracts of *Psidium guajava* leaves, as well as a comparison of phytochemical screening among all extracts (i.e., Aqueous, Methanolic and Ethanolic Extracts of *Psidium guajava*). Fresh leaves of *Psidium guajava* were collected and shade dried for 10 days. Dried leaves were subjected and grounded to size reduction, followed by passing through sieve no. 40. Aqueous extract was prepared by Decoction method. Maceration method is used to prepare the Ethanolic and Methanolic extracts. For Organoleptic characteristic investigation, fresh leaves of *Psidium guajava* were used. Presence of phytoconstituents was found to be more in aqueous extracts as compared to ethanolic and Methanolic extracts. But beside these, all three extracts were found to be the presence of various phytochemical constituents such as Alkaloids, Tannins, Saponins, Flavonoids, Saponin Glycosides, Cardiac Glycosides, Steroids etc. Percentage yield of aqueous extract was much better as compared to both Methanolic and Ethanolic extracts. *Psidium guajava* leaves may be identified and standardised using a quick, efficient, and affordable process that involves the study of numerous physicochemical constants. The results of the qualitative phytochemical analysis showed that the leaf's aqueous extract contains several secondary plant compounds with significant therapeutic efficacy. Hence, *Psidium guajava* leaf aqueous extracts can be employed to isolate beneficial secondary plant compounds for further drug development. This might be used as a basic medicine quality control and authentication measure.

Keywords: *Psidium Guajava*, Phytoconstituents, Methanolic Extract, Ethanolic extract, Aqueous Extract

INTRODUCTION

South America is home to the *Psidium guajava* plant, which is also indigenous to India, Nepal, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Malaysia, Thailand, Brazil, Florida, and the West Indies. It is a member of the Myrtaceae family and is generally referred to as guava. *Psidium guajava* is a small, Fruit Producing, Shrub, Having opposite and Aromatic Short- petiole leaves. It also has a great medicinal and therapeutics value. Guava plant is also used in various medicinal conditions such as Wounds, Ulcers, cough, fever, Fungal infections, Skin Infections etc. *Psidium guajava* possesses various pharmacological activities such as Anti-oxidants, Anti-Ulcers, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Microbial, Anti-spasmodic, Antipyretic, Anti-Inflammatory, Antifungal etc. From ancient times, Guava plant is used as medicinal plant worldwide. For many years, plants have been a rich source of medicinal

substances. As a consequence of public views that these phyto-medicines are secure, conveniently accessible, affordable, and have fewer adverse effects, natural medicines have grown in popularity in the treatment of a variety of illnesses. Several plant-based medicines are more reasonably priced and widely available than conventional drugs. Few harmful consequences remain after usage. They may be used and noticed widely as a result of these reasons. Medicinal plants are the main source of new pharmaceutical and healthcare products. With the extraction and characterization of several strong phytocompounds, these "green factories" have created some well-known medications [1-2]. The plant *Psidium guajava* grows well in tropical and subtropical environments. The principal traditional use has been as an anti-diarrheal, but other reported applications include dysentery, gastroenteritis,

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stomach, and antibacterial colic pathogenic germs of the intestines [3]. *Psidium guajava* is a tiny tree that can reach a height of 20 feet and has spreading branches. The guava tree is renowned for its appealing, "bony" look of its trunk, which over time may extend to a diameter of 10 inches [3-4], and for its smooth, thin, copper-colored bark that peels off to reveal the layer of greenish tissue behind it. Thought to be native to Mexico, the plant *Psidium guajava* is also found in South America, Africa, Europe, and Asia [5].

Taxonomical Classification of *Psidium guajava* leaf

- **Kingdom** : *Plantae*
- **Order** : *Myrtales*
- **Family** : *Myrtaceae*
- **Subfamily** : *Piperoideae*
- **Genus** : *Psidium L.*
- **Species** : *Guajava L*
- **Division** : *Magnoliphyta* [6]

Chemical Constitution of *Psidium guajava*. leaf

The leaf of *Psidium guajava*. leaf has been composed of following chemical constituent, which are beneficial for various medical conditions. Table 1.0 compiles the list of chemical compounds found in leaf [7, 8,9].

Table 1.0: List of chemical constituent present in *Psidium guajava*. Leaf [10]

Sr. no.	Chemical constituent
1.	α -pinene
2.	Limonene
3.	β -Pinene
4.	Isopropyl Alcohol
5.	Menthol
6.	Terpenyl Acetate
7.	Caryophyllene
8.	Longicyclene
9.	β -Biosolene
10.	Other Volatile compounds

The significance of *Psidium guajava* leaf extract in terms of medicine

Psidium guajava leaf extracts in aqueous, methanolic, and ethanolic forms have been studied for their potential medicinal and pharmacological effects. In the following vertical chevron list that are provided

below, the list of numerous pharmacological benefits has been compiled.

1.	• Anti-Hypertensive
2.	• Anti-ulcer
3.	• Anti-diabetic
4.	• Analgesic
5.	• Anti-oxidant
6.	• Anti-inflammatory
7.	• Anti-microbial
8.	• Anti-Cough
9.	• Antidiarrheal [11-14]

Fig. no. 1.: Pharmacological activities investigated in extracts of *Psidium guajava* leaves. [15-18]

Common name for *Psidium guajava*

Psidium guajava is known by various vernacular names according to traditional system of medicine. In India, Multiple languages are spoken, so *Psidium guajava* also have some synonyms name. The given table (Table 2.0) compiles all the data.

Table 2.0: List of Vernacular or Common names of *Psidium guajava* leaf [19-20]

Sr. No.	Traditional system of Medicine or other Indian Languages	Vernacular names
1.	Hindi, Urdu	Amrud
2.	Sanskrit	Beejapooram
3.	Unani	Amrud
4.	Ayurveda	Mukhapaka
5.	Bengali	Peyara
6.	Gujarati	Paan

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Procurement of Plant material

Psidium guajava leaves were collected from the Local market of Dubagga, Lucknow. The leaf was authenticated by Dr Shashank Tiwari, Director (Academic and Research), Lucknow Model College of Pharmacy and Research, Lucknow.

The leaves were washed through tap water to remove dirt and attached impure particles and kept for air and shade dried for 15 days, grounded for size reduction by Grinder and subjected to size separation by Sieve no. 40 to get fine powder. Resulting Fine Powder was obtained, kept for further Studies by packing in zipper bags, followed by placing them in Desiccators.

Organoleptic Evaluation of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

During conducting an organoleptic examination, some sensory factors were noted, including odour, colour, taste, shape, apex, and leaf texture.

Preparation of Extracts

Fresh, washed, and dried leaves of *Psidium guajava* were pulverised to create coarse powder, which was then passed through Sieve No. 40 to separate the particles by size. *Psidium guajava* leaves were then ground into a fine powder as an outcome.

1. Preparation of Aqueous Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

The fresh, washed, and dried leaves of *Psidium guajava* were processed into an aqueous extract using the decoction technique. After grinding the leaves into a coarse powder, the coarse powder was separated into different sizes by being passed through Sieve No. 40. *Psidium guajava* leaves were ground into a fine powder. By mixing 10 gm of finely powdered *Psidium guajava* Leaves with 100 ml of distilled water in a 500 ml beaker, an aqueous extract of the plant was created. On a heating mantle, the mixture was boiled for 15 minutes at 80 degrees. Beaker was then taken out of the heating mantle and let to sit at room temperature. Whatman Filter Paper No. 1 was used to filter the mixture. The resulting mixture was then placed into a petri dish, and water was then evaporated using a water bath at 80°C.

2. Preparation of Methanolic Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

Fresh, washed, and dried leaves of *Psidium guajava* were macerated to create a methanolic extract. After grinding the leaves into a coarse powder, the coarse powder was separated into different sizes by being passed through Sieve No. 40. As a consequence, *Psidium guajava* leaves were ground into a fine powder. *Psidium guajava* leaves were pulverized into a fine powder and placed in a 250-milliliter volumetric flask constructed of borosilicate glass together with 100 ml of methanol in order to create a methanolic extract. stored this concoction in reserve for 96 hours. After this step, the mixture is filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 1 to remove any

remaining impurities. The resulting mixture was placed onto a petri dish, and then Methanol was evaporated using a water bath at 80°C.

3. Preparation of Ethanolic Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

Freshly, rinsed, and dried leaves of *Psidium guajava* were macerated to create an ethanol extract. After grinding the leaves into a coarse powder, the coarse powder was separated into different sizes by being passed through Sieve No. 40. As a consequence, *Psidium guajava* leaves were ground into a fine powder. *Psidium guajava* leaf ethanolic extract was made by combining 10 gm of finely powdered leaves with 100 ml of ethanol in a 250 ml volumetric flask made of borosilicate glass. stored this concoction in reserve for 96 hours. Whatman filter paper No. 1 is then used to filter the mixture after this step. The resulting mixture was put onto a petri dish, and then the ethanol was evaporated using an 80°C water bath.

4. Preparation of Acetone Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

Percolation was used to create an acetone extract from fresh, cleansed, and dried leaves of *Psidium guajava*. The leaves were then pulverised to make coarser powder, which was then size differentiated by passing the coarse powder with Sieve no. 40. As an outcome, *Psidium guajava* leaf powder was generated. Acetone extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves was created by consuming 10 gm of fine powdered *Psidium guajava* Leaves while using Acetone as a solvent [22].

Qualitative Phytochemical screening or analysis of *Psidium guajava* leaf extracts

All three extracts (i.e., Aqueous, Methanolic, Ethanolic extracts) are subjected to various Phytochemical screening tests for determining the presence the various Phytochemical or phytoconstituents such as Alkaloids, Glycosides, Triterpenoids, Flavonoids, Phenolic compounds, Steroids, Cardiac glycosides etc. by using various standard methods. The analyzed compounds were Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Anthro-quinone, Saponins, Carbohydrates, volatile oils, Saponin glycosides, Cardiac Glycosides, Tannins, Steroids etc.

1. Mayer's test:

Solvent free extracts were stirred with one ml of dilute Hydrochloric acid and followed by the addition of the few drops of Mayer's Reagent. Organic Reddish Brown coloured precipitate or Cream color confirms the presence of the alkaloids.

2. Wagner's test:

Solvent free extracts were stirred with one ml of dilute Hydrochloric acid and followed by the addition of the few drops of Wagner's Reagent. Brown or Reddish-brown coloured precipitate confirms the presence of the alkaloids.

3. Dragendorff's test:

Extracts were stirred with few drops of Dragendorff's Reagent. Reddish Brown colour or precipitate confirms the presence of the alkaloids.

4. Flavonoid test: (Alkaline Reagent Test)

All extracts were diluted with distilled water. Then, all aqueous extracts were treated with 1 ml of diluted Ammonium hydroxide solution, showed fluorescence of yellow colour which gets disappear on the addition of acid. Fluorescence of yellow coloured confirms the presence of flavonoids.

5. Cardiac Glycosides test:

Distilled water is used to dilute the aqueous, methanolic, and ethanolic extracts individually. The extract solution was then treated with a 3.5% solution of ferric chloride. Allow to stand for 1-2 minutes. Add few drops of Conc. H_2SO_4 by the wall of the test tubes. A Reddish- Brown Colour is formed at Junctions which turns blue after few minutes confirm the presences of Cardiac Glycosides.

6. Saponin glycosides test:

Fehling Solution "A" and "B" was added in 2.5 ml solution of extracts.

7. Saponin test:

0.5 gm of extracted was diluted with 5 ml of water. Shake well the test tube for few minutes. Froths generation or 1 Cm layer of foam confirms the presence of Saponin.

8. Tannins Test:

2ml of all extracts solutions was treated with 5% Ferric Chloride solution gradually. Blue colour was obtained. On addition of more Ferric chloride solution, blue colour turns into Olive green. It confirms the presence of Tannins.

9. Molisch Test:

All extracts are diluted with water. All solutions were treated with Molisch reagent. Conc. Sulphuric acid was also added along the side of the test tubes. A purple ring at the junction confirms the presence of Carbohydrates.

10. Test for Anthraquinones:

All solutions of the extracts was treated with 10 ml benzene, and 10% Ammonia Solution. Shake the Test tubes well to confirms the colour of Anthraquinones.

11. Test for Steroids:

According to the Harborne method (1973), Diluted samples of extracts (2 ml) was treated with chloroform (2ml). Allow to stand for 1-2 minutes followed by the addition of Conc. Sulphuric Acid along the wall of test tubes to form the lower layer.

12. Test for Volatile oils:

1 ml of each diluted samples of extracts were mixed with HCl. White precipitate formation confirms the presence of the Volatile oils [23, 24].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Preparation of Extracts of *Psidium guajava* Leaf

Preparation of Aqueous Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

The concentrated extract (1.21 gm, solid, dark brown in colour) was preserved in desiccators for future usage and stored in sample bottles.

Preparation of Methanolic Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

The concentrated extract (1.71 gm, solid, dark green in colour) was preserved in desiccators for future usage and stored in sample bottles.

Preparation of Ethanolic Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

The concentrated extract (1.63 gm, solid, dark green in colour) was preserved in desiccators for future usage and stored in sample bottles.

Preparation of Acetone Extract of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

The concentrated extract (0.51 gm, solid, Green in colour) was preserved in desiccators for future usage and stored in sample bottles.

2. Percentage Yield of various extracts of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

Different percentage yields, colours, and states are present in each of the three *Psidium guajava* leaf extracts. The analysis's findings are summarised in the table below. (Table 3.0).

Table 3.0: Percentage Yield of various extracts of *Psidium guajava* Leaves

Sr. no.	Extract	Extraction method	Yield (in gm)	% yield	Colour	State
1.	Aqueous	Decoction	1.21 gm	12.1 %	Dark Brown	Solid
2.	Methanolic	Maceration	1.71 gm	17.1%	Dark green	Solid
3.	Ethanolic	Maceration	1.63 gm	16.3%	Dark green	Solid
4.	Acetone	Percolation	0.51	5.1%	Green	Solid

3. Morphological or Organoleptic properties of *Psidium guajava* leaves

Psidium guajava leaves were studied for their morphological and organoleptic qualities. Table 4.0 summarises the findings of the examination.

Table 4.0: Morphological or Organoleptic properties of *Psidium guajava* leaves

Sr. No.	Morphological characteristics	Observation data
1.	Dimension of leaf	Length: 4-16 cm Width: 4-7 cm
2.	Colour and Condition	Fresh leaf: Green-pale green
3.	Lamina	Green, Reticulate, simple
4.	Shape	Elliptical, Oval
5.	Odour	Aromatic
6.	Texture	Leathery
7.	Venation	Pinnate Reticulate
8.	Apex	Ovate
9.	Taste	Aromatic

4. Phytochemical screening OR Phytoconstituent screening

phytoconstituent in extracts of *Psidium guajava* leaves. The result of this investigation is listed below.

Table 5.0: Phytochemical screening of *Psidium guajava* leaves

Sr. No.	Test name	Aqueous extract	Methanolic extract	Ethanolic extract	Acetone extract
1.	Mayer's test	-	-	-	-
2.	Wagner's test	+	+	-	-
3.	Dragendroff's Test	-	-	+	-
4.	Flavonoids test	+	-	-	+
5.	Tannin test	+	+	+	+
6.	Test for Cardiac Glycosides	+	+	+	+
7.	Test for Saponin Glycosides	+	+	-	+
8.	Saponin test	+	+	+	+
9.	Molisch test	+	+	+	-
10.	Test for Anthraquinone	-	-	-	-

11.	Steroid test	+	+	+	-
12.	Volatile oils	+	-	-	-

Whereas “+” indicates for the presence and “-” indicate the absence of that phytoconstituents

IMAGES

CONCLUSION

The current investigation demonstrates that the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, steroid, anthraquinones, Carbohydrates, saponins, cardiac glycosides and Saponin Glycosides which may be responsible for a variety of medicinal and therapeutic activities, was reported by the phytochemical screening. Because to the maximum presence of many phytoconstituents in aqueous extract of *Psidium guajava*, there is a lot of potential for in vivo investigations. Thus, Aqueous extract is ready and much better for further Research Purposes.

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